

Ethno-Vlog Information Technology as an Interactive Learning Media Integrated with Local Knowledge

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ABSTRACT

Innovation and creation of learning media must continue to be carried out by a teacher so that the learning process remains relevant to the times. Vlog is one of the effective contemporary learning media. This can be done through integrating the knowledge that develops in the local community and presenting it into learning media to make it easier to relate the concept of learning to life. The integration of knowledge that develops in the local community into the learning presented through vlogs is known as ethno-vlog. Currently, teachers in the field are not familiar with learning media in the form of ethno-vlogs. Socialization of ethno-vlogs is carried out to provide understanding and increase insight for partners regarding learning media in the form of vlogs that are integrated with the knowledge or culture of the local community known as ethnosains. Based on the results of the posttest above, it is known that the partner already knows what ethnosains, vlogs, ethno-vlogs, and how to make ethno-vlogs. After participating in the socialization, participants have learned the concept of reconstructing ethnosains into the form of ethno-vlogs and participants have learned how to relate ethno-vlogs in a learning material and feel that this ethno-vlog socialization activity as a learning medium is very beneficial for participants. This can be seen from the results of the posttest questionnaire given, which obtained a score of 100% each. Based on the results of the pretest and posttest of the ethno-vlog socialization activity as a contemporary learning media integrated with local knowledge, it can be stated that this activity is successful and can increase insight and ability to plan learning media.

Keywords: Ethnosains; Ethno-Vlog; Learning Media

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the development of information and communication technology is felt very rapidly. Almost all activities are controlled by technology. This requires all parties to be able to adapt and develop themselves to follow it. The impact of this technological development without exception requires the education sector to continue to adapt. Technological developments require educators or teachers to have various innovations and creativity so that the learning process can be relevant to the times (Dewi et al., 2019). Educators are required to switch, change, and develop themselves inventively and creatively as creators and facilitators of the learning process. Choosing the right media will help educators deliver learning materials. Currently, there are many information technology-based learning media that are available to be used and facilitate the learning process. Learning media that is integrated in information technology can make its own attraction and be able to motivate students. The use of the internet today is mostly for entertainment purposes only. If this is not addressed, it will very likely have an impact on student learning outcomes. Of course, it takes innovation and creativity of an educator to anticipate this. Building blog-based learning media is one of the innovations that can be applied. When educators provide materials that students can access even before the learning process begins, it will allow students to better understand the material to be learned. The presence of vlogs or video blogs which is a type of information media in the form of videos that are packaged in a simple way that is managed through blogs and youtube, is currently causing the media to "blog" to grow (Atmojo et al., 2018).

Vlogs "can be used as an effective learning medium to increase students' interest in learning. According to Vlogs "make it easier for people to convey thoughts, feelings and information through visual platforms. Vlog enthusiasts have spread to various circles that are used as a source of information, entertainment, and so on. Therefore, educators can use Vlogs as a learning medium by displaying videos of learning materials in an interesting way, which can create interactive, interesting and fun learning conditions, so that they can motivate students to learn and provide a good learning experience. Ethno-vlog "is one of the alternatives that can be developed as a learning medium that is able to integrate local knowledge values into learning materials, especially science learning (ethnoscience). Ethnoscience can be integrated into learning in schools with various learning themes. In addition to preserving local culture, ethnoscience learning is considered to improve the quality of education and character of students. One example of developing vlogs as an ethnoscience-based learning media has been carried out developing ethnologs on the material on the Basic Competency of traditional biotechnology by analyzing typical foods, namely the fermentation of shrimp into a typical food called cencaluk. The involvement of local knowledge or local wisdom is very necessary in a learning process. So far, the learning process has studied more examples that are not

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directly experienced by students. It would be better for students to experience the learning process directly, so that students are not pseudo-intelligent but understand meaningfully in learning a subject matter (Parmin et al., 2019).

Madrasah Aliyah is one of the high schools in the region. This school has a vision as a madrasah that is superior, competitive, dignified, personal and social justice and love for the environment. Administratively, this school is still relatively new, which was inaugurated. As a new school, of course, it really needs to improve learning programs that are able to compete with other schools, especially other big cities. To support the vision of Madrasah Aliyah, of course, the role of teachers in learning students well is very important. Teachers must be able to design learning media by considering the characteristics and cultural background of their students because education always contains values that must be in accordance with the values that apply in the society where they are (Nambiar, 2017). Learning materials that are presented by supporting students' perspective on the surrounding nature (inculturation) will make learning more interesting so that it can increase student understanding and ultimately learning will be more meaningful. In the current condition, teachers at Madrasah Aliyah have never implemented ethno-vlogging as a learning medium that integrates ethnoscience into blogger videos. With the socialization of ethnography as a contemporary learning media that integrates local knowledge, it is hoped that it will contribute to the achievement of the vision and development of the school

RESEARCH ELABORATIONS

The method of implementing this activity is carried out based on the following steps. The implementation team conducted a situation analysis in the form of field surveys and interviews with teachers and curriculum representatives of Madrasah Aliyah. The implementation team prepares proposals for community service activities. The implementation team carried out socialization activities in the form of the introduction of ethno-vlogs as a learning medium. Socialization activities are planned through face-to-face. Evaluation of the implementation of the program is carried out by providing questionnaires before and after the implementation of socialization activities to see and find out the extent of the insight and understanding of the participants of the activity on the material delivered by the presenter (service implementation team). This is from the results of the pretest postes questionnaire given by the team to the socialization participants. Furthermore, the data will be analyzed with a descriptive percentage. In addition, the implementation team can find out what local wisdom plans will be made by teachers as a learning medium So, the service team gets more measurable feedback for the

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progress of this service activity program in the future. The implementation team made a conclusion on the results of the socialization activities.

This community service activity is designed with a systematic and measurable approach, starting with a comprehensive analysis of the situation. The implementation team conducted a field review and in-depth interviews with teachers and curriculum representatives of Madrasah Aliyah. This stage is crucial to understand the specific needs, challenges faced, and the potential use of ethno-vlogs as a learning medium. The information gathered from this initial analysis becomes a strong basis in the preparation of proposals for community service activities, ensuring the relevance and sustainability of the program to be implemented.

After the proposal was approved, the focus shifted to socializing ethno-vlogs as a learning medium. This socialization activity is planned face-to-face, allowing direct interaction between the implementation team and participants. This method was chosen to facilitate better understanding, effective Q&A sessions, and practical demonstrations of how to create and utilize ethno-vlogs. It is hoped that, through this hands-on approach, participants can gain the in-depth insights and initial skills needed to integrate ethno-vlogs in the teaching and learning process.

Evaluation of program implementation is an integral element to measure the impact and effectiveness of activities. The evaluation process was carried out quantitatively by providing pretest and posttest questionnaires to socialization participants. The pretest questionnaire was given before the activity to measure the level of knowledge and initial understanding of participants about ethno-vlogs and their potential as a learning medium. Meanwhile, a posttest questionnaire was given after the socialization was completed to assess the extent of increased insight and understanding achieved by the participants after receiving material from the presenter.

The data collected from the pretest and posttest questionnaires will then be analyzed in a descriptive percentage manner. This analysis will provide a clear picture of changes in participants' level of understanding before and after socialization. In addition, information will also be explored from the questionnaire about what local wisdom plans will be made by teachers as a learning medium. This information is invaluable because it shows the level of acceptance and application of the ethno-vlog concept in the context of local wisdom by teachers.

With a combination of quantitative evaluation through questionnaires and percentage descriptive analysis, the service team will get more measurable feedback. This feedback not only provides an indication of the success of the ongoing program, but also becomes an important foundation for the progress of this service program in the future. Information on participants' understanding and local wisdom implementation plans will be valuable guides in

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designing more relevant, effective, and sustainable follow-up activities, ensuring an ever-increasing positive impact on the world of education

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Community Service entitled "Socialization of Ethno-Vlog as a Contemporary Learning Media Integrated with Local Knowledge" was held on Friday, January 20, 2023. The participants of this training consisted of 24 teachers who taught at the school. The resource persons in this activity were the Service Team. The training was held starting at 09.00 WIB and ended at 12.00 WIB. This training is divided into 2 sessions. Session 1 was a presentation of material on what ethno-vlogs are, why to use ethno-vlogs, and how to integrate ethnoscience in learning vlogs, followed by questions and answers and discussions. The material was delivered This activity started from 09.00 - 10.30 WIB. At the beginning of this activity session, it began with a speech from the principal.

The next activity was the opening remarks from the Head of the Service Team providing motivation regarding the real benefits that will be obtained by partners through the activities that will be carried out After giving motivation by the head of the Service Team, then a pretest sheet was given to the trainees to measure the participants' initial knowledge of the material to be explained. As seen in the following Figure 3. During session 1, the partners seemed enthusiastic in participating in the activity. This can be seen from the questions and answers to the speakers and the discussion flowed smoothly from the activity partners. Many questions were asked about ethno-vlogs and these questions were answered by the team leader and were also answered by members of the Service Team as seen after session 1 activity was completed, followed by session 2 which was a presentation of ethno-vlog examples and reconstruction of original science to scientific science. This training is guided by the entire service team This activity starts from 10.30 - 12.00 WIB. In session 2, participants looked enthusiastic to see examples of ethno-vlog applications as learning media. Many questions were asked by partners regarding the creation of ethno-vlogs on the sidelines of media broadcasts. The activity in session 2 also actively involved partners, namely by providing opportunities for participants to provide ethnoscience study plans that can be applied to the subjects taught. In the presentation of this ethno-vlog example, it is learned how to reconstruct original science that develops in society into scientific science that can be applied in learning.

Participants were given posttest sheets to evaluate the level of understanding of partners regarding the material that had been obtained and carried out. The following is some documentation of the implementation of service activities by the Team After the socialization activities are completed, the service team processes the pretest and posttest data that have been

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obtained for further analysis with descriptive percentages. The results of the initial understanding of the socialization participants or service partner teachers obtained by using the pretest questionnaire can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. Pretest Results of Socialization Participants

No	Pertanyaan	%	
		Yes	No
1	Do participants know what ethnosience is??	14,81	85,19
2	Do participants know what a vlog is?	92,59	7,41
3	Do participants know what ethno-vlogging is?	11,11	88,89
4	Do participants know the learning media?	96,30	3,70
5	Do participants know that ethno-vlogs can be used as a learning medium?	14,81	85,19
6	Do participants know how to make an ethno-vlog?	0	100
7	Do participants know the concept of reconstructing ethnosience into the form of ethno-vlogs?	0	100
8	Is this ethno-vlog socialization activity as a learning medium useful for participants?	74,07	25,93
9	After the socialization activity, participants will try to use ethnolog as a learning medium?	92,59	7,41
10	Do participants know how to relate ethno-vlogs in a learning material?	0	100

Source: Query processing

Based on the results of the pretest above, it is known that most of the participants (85.19%) do not know what ethnosience is. Only 7.41% of participants did not know about vlogs, but most of the participants did not know about ethno-vlogs, which was 88.89% but had heard that Ethno-vlogs could be used as a learning medium, which was 85.19%. The concept of reconstructing ethnosience into the form of ethno-vlogging, linking ethno-vlogs into learning materials and how to make ethno-vlogs is not yet known to the participants, this can be seen from the questionnaire value that was answered, which stated not as much as 100%. A total of 74.07% stated that ethno-vlog socialization activities as a learning medium were beneficial for participants and as many as 92.59% of participants stated that After the socialization activity, participants would try to use ethno-vlog as a learning medium. From these results, it can be concluded that most partners do not have prior knowledge of what it is

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Ethno-vlogs and how to make them so that this service activity is indeed needed by partners. After socialization, a posttest was given to partners which aimed to find out the final knowledge of the participants after being given knowledge about ethno-vlogs. The partner's final knowledge can be seen in the following table:

Table 2. Posttest Results of Service Partners

No	Question	%	
		Yes	No
1	Do participants know what ethnosience is??	100	0
2	Do participants know what a vlog is?	100	0
3	Do participants know what ethno-vlogging is?	100	0
4	Do participants know the learning media?	100	0
5	Do participants know that ethno-vlogs can be used as a learning medium?	100	0
6	Do participants know how to make an ethno-vlog?	100	0
7	Do participants know the concept of reconstructing ethnosience into the form of ethno-vlogs?	100	0
8	Is this ethno-vlog socialization activity as a learning medium useful for participants?	100	0
9	After the socialization activity, participants will try to use ethnolog as a learning medium?	81,48	18,52
10	Do participants know how to relate ethno-vlogs in a learning material?	100	0

Source: Question Results

Based on the results of the posttest above, it is known that partners already know what ethnosience, vlogs, ethno-vlogs, and how to make ethno-vlogs. After participating in the socialization, participants have learned the concept of reconstructing ethnosience into the form of ethno-vlogs and participants have learned how to relate ethno-vlogs in a learning material and feel that ethno-vlog socialization activities As a learning medium are very useful for participants, this can be seen from the results of the posttest questionnaire that was given to obtain a score of 100% each. With an understanding of ethnographic media reaching 100%, it means that this socialization can be said to be successful well. However, with the questionnaire question whether participants After the socialization activity will try to use ethnovlog as a learning medium, most participants answered that they would use ethnovlog as a learning medium by 81.48%.

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As a Contemporary Learning Media Integrated with Local Knowledge, this has been successful. This can be seen from the percentage of the participant's posttest score and what local wisdom plan will be used by the participant as an Ethno-Vlog Learning Media. By integrating local culture and wisdom into learning, students are trained to observe directly and discover various concepts comprehensively and meaningfully so as to provide the scientific knowledge contained in the value of science. In the end, it can encourage them to explore what is contained in local wisdom.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of pretests and posters that have been given before and after the socialization of Ethnovlog as a Contemporary Learning Media Integrated Local Knowledge, it can be stated that this activity was successful and can increase insight and ability to plan learning media in the form of Ethnovlog integrated with local wisdom. It is known that 100% of partners already know what ethnosience, vlogs, ethnologs, and how to make ethno-vlogs. After participating in the socialization, participants have learned the concept of reconstructing ethnosience into the form of ethno-vlogs and participants have learned how to relate ethno-vlogs in a learning material and feel that ethno-vlog socialization activities as a learning medium are very beneficial for participants. Based on the follow-up questions given, the participants already had an idea to create a learning ethnolog based on the local wisdom of their respective regions. Based on the evaluation that has been carried out, it can be seen that this socialization activity has a positive impact on partners. Furthermore, it is necessary to conduct technical assistance training for partners in creating Ethnovlog and reconstructing the original science of the scientific community from the local wisdom plan that has been selected, so that it can be used as a contemporary learning medium.

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